

Fiber-Optic Links with All-Photonic RF Gain and Low RF Noise Figure

Vincent J. Urick, Jason D. McKinney, John F. Diehl, and Keith J. Williams

Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC USA

Abstract — State-of-the-art analog fiber-optic links exhibiting electronic power gain and/or electronic noise figure less than 20 dB at frequencies higher than 1 GHz are demonstrated and reviewed.

Index Terms — Microwave photonics, noise figure (NF).

I. INTRODUCTION

Analog photonics remains an important field by fulfilling requirements in numerous applications where digital electronics are lacking. Compared to an electronic radio-frequency (RF) link, the electrical-to-optical-to-electrical conversion process in an analog photonic link can impose loss that will be greater than that for an RF link unless the transmission distance is long, leveraging low-loss optical fiber. Traditionally, a low-noise amplifier (LNA) will be employed on the front-end of an analog optical link, reducing the cascaded noise figure (NF) while taking advantage of the low-loss optical fiber. However, a low-NF and high-gain analog optical link without an RF LNA is attractive for applications such as integrated antennas with a photonic balun, high-power-handling front ends [1], high-efficiency RF power remoting [2] and optoelectronic oscillators [3].

In this work we survey the present state of the art for high-gain and low-noise analog optical links, including three new experiments employing high-performance components. Each of these experiments employs different external-modulation architectures and serves to demonstrate the performance as a function of component metrics.

II. DEMONSTRATED CAPABILITIES

Low-NF and high-gain analog optical links have been cataloged previously [4],[5]. Here, we provide the results of a survey with updates to [4] and [5] including data since April 2009 and those in Section III below. We restrict the present survey to analog optical links demonstrating all-photonic RF gain $G \geq 0$ dB (Fig. 1) and/or NF ≤ 20 dB (Fig. 2) at frequencies at or above 1 GHz, noting that additional information outside these bounds is provided in [4] and [5].

As can be seen in Figs. 1 and 2, there have been numerous demonstrations of high- G , low-noise photonic links. A variety of architectures have been employed to that end, including direct intensity modulation of lasers with direct detection [6], external differential intensity modulation with balanced detection [8],[9],[11],[12], external modulation with

Fig. 1. A survey of analog optical links with $G \geq 0$ dB at frequencies at or above 1 GHz. Solid lines are an interpolation between points extracted from the literature. The dashed lines are for phase-modulated links demonstrated in Section (§) III C and designate that the links operate only at the points shown.

Fig. 2. A survey of analog optical links with NF ≤ 20 dB at frequencies at or above 1 GHz. Solid lines are an interpolation between points extracted from the literature. The dashed line is for a phase-modulated link demonstrated in Section (§) III C and designates that the link operates only at the points shown.

Fig. 3. Apparatus for intensity modulation with balanced detection.

Fig. 4. The measured NF (black) and G (gray) for the differential intensity modulation with balanced detection link.

low-biased Mach-Zehnder modulators and direct detection [10],[12]-[14],[16], cascaded external modulators [15] and coherent receivers [17]. Two of these approaches are demonstrated in Section III along with phase modulation. Whatever the architecture, the performance will depend heavily on component parameters with the most important being the amount of optical power available, the optically-generated noise, the optical power handling of the external modulators (if used) and photodiodes, and the efficiency of the modulation and demodulation.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Three external modulation architectures are demonstrated to achieve low NF and high G without the use of electronic amplification. In each case, the important parameters are highlighted and experiment is shown to agree with theory.

A. Differential Intensity Modulation with Balanced Detection

The architecture for differential external intensity modulation with balanced detection [8],[9],[11],[12] is shown in Fig. 3. In these experiments, a 60-mW distributed feedback (DFB) semiconductor laser (JDSU CQF938) is amplified with a 1-W polarization maintaining (PM) erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA, PriTel PMFA-30) and injected into a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM, EOSPACE AZ-2x2-PFU-PFU-NRL). With the MZM biased at quadrature, an equal amount of optical power is delivered to two p-i-n photodiodes

(Discovery Semiconductor DSC50S) that are combined with an RF hybrid coupler for balanced detection. As shown in Fig. 3, the phase between the two arms was controlled by variable optical delay lines and the two photodiodes had an equivalent 50- Ω parallel resistance in the RF path for matching to the load. Note that the differential detection can also be implemented with a balanced receiver (see Fig. 7).

In the case of a true balanced receiver, the maximum RF gain factor (g) for a differential intensity modulation with balanced detection link is given by

$$g = \pi^2 \left(\frac{I_{dc}^2}{V_{\pi}^2} \right) R_{in} R_{out}, \quad (1)$$

where I_{dc} is the total DC photocurrent ($I_{dc}/2$ per diode), V_{π} is the frequency-dependent MZM half-wave voltage, R_{in} is the MZM resistance (matched to the input source), and R_{out} is the load resistance. The assumptions in (1) are that the gain is not resonantly enhanced, all input RF voltage is applied to the MZM electrodes, the photodiode is an ideal current source and there is no excess RF loss. With these assumptions and further assuming that only thermal and shot noise contribute, the minimum RF noise factor (F) is

$$F = 1 + \frac{V_{\pi}^2}{\pi^2 R_{in}} \left(\frac{1}{I_{dc}^2 R_{out}} + \frac{2e}{I_{dc} k_B T} \right) \quad (2)$$

where e is the electron charge constant, k_B is Boltzmann's constant and $T = 290$ K is the standard temperature. The first term in (2) is due to thermal noise at the link input transferred to the output, with the second accounting for thermal noise at the link output and the third term being due to shot noise.

The experimental results are shown in Fig. 4 with the NF results summarized in Fig. 2. The G was measured with a network analyzer (HP 8510) and the NF was obtained by using the measured G and measuring the output noise with an electrical spectrum analyzer (Agilent 8563EC). Though the link exhibits loss across all frequencies shown, the NF approaches 10 dB in the 2-10 GHz range, which is among the best results reported to date. For these data, $I_{dc} = 20$ mA (10 mA per diode) and $V_{\pi} = 1.35$ V at 6 GHz. Accounting for 6-dB loss due to the photodiode matching circuits and 3-dB intrinsic loss in the RF hybrid, (1) predicts $G = -1.7$ dB for these parameters with $R_{in} = R_{out} = 50 \Omega$. This compares nicely with the measured $G = -3$ dB, with the error being attributed to excess loss in the hybrid. With a factor of about 10.7 (10.3 dB) applied to the second term in (2), which handles the hybrid loss and loss in the photodiode circuits, the calculated NF = 12.5 dB at 6 GHz. This is in excellent agreement with the measured NF = 12 dB at 6 GHz and also demonstrates that the noise due to optical amplification has been balanced.

Fig. 5. Apparatus for a low-biased analog optical link.

Fig. 6. Measured NF (black) and G (gray) for the low-biased link.

B. Low-Biased Mach-Zehnder Modulator

The setup for the low-biased link employing pre-MZM optical amplification [12]-[14] is shown in Fig. 5, noting that interesting results have also been obtained with low-biased links employing post-MZM optical amplification [10],[16]. The same DFB laser and EDFA as in Section IIIA were employed with a different dual-output MZM (EOSPACE AZ-1x2-PFU-SFU-ULTRA). The low-biased MZM output is then fed to a p-i-n photodiode (Discovery Semiconductor DSC50).

With the same assumptions as for (1), the g for such a link as a function of bias is given by

$$g = \pi^2 \left(\frac{I_{dc,q}^2}{V_\pi^2} \right) R_{in} R_{out} \sin^2 \phi_{dc}, \quad (3)$$

where $I_{dc,q} = \Re \alpha_m P_o / 2$ is the DC photocurrent at quadrature and $\phi_{dc} = \pi V_{dc} / V_\pi$ is the relative phase shift due to the DC bias voltage V_{dc} . Here, \Re is the diode responsivity, α_m is the MZM optical loss, and P_o is the optical power at the MZM input. The thermal- and shot-noise-limited F is then

$$F = 1 + \frac{V_\pi^2}{\pi^2 R_{in} \sin^2 \phi_{dc}} \left[\frac{1}{I_{dc,q}^2 R_{out}} + \frac{2e(1 - \cos \phi_{dc})}{I_{dc,q} k_B T} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Fig. 7. Architecture for a phase-modulated analog optical link.

Fig. 8. Measured NF (diamonds) and G (lines) for the link in Fig. 7 with the EDFA before (gray) and after (black) the modulator.

The results of this experiment are shown in Fig. 6 with the parameters $\Re = 0.72$ A/W, $\alpha_m = 0.234$ (-6.3 dB), $P_o = 1$ W, $R_{in} = R_{out} = 50 \Omega$, and $V_\pi = 1.1$ V at 1 GHz. The MZM bias was adjusted to minimize the NF, which was measured along with G using a noise figure meter (HP 8970B). As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, these results are on par with the state of the art but come at the cost of even-order distortion due to the low-biasing. The empirically-determined bias to minimize the NF yielded $\phi_{dc} = 0.085\pi$. With the parameters above, the calculated $G = 10.1$ and $NF = 3.6$, as compared to the measured $G = 10.5$ dB and $NF = 6$ dB at 1 GHz. Therefore, in this case the NF penalty incurred due to optical amplification is 2.4 dB. Furthermore, the optimum theoretical bias point yields $\phi_{dc} = 0.124\pi$, which gives a minimal improvement in the theoretical $NF = 3.5$ dB but a significant increase in gain to $G = 13$ dB.

C. Phase Modulation

The architecture for phase modulation employing an asymmetric Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI) and balanced photodiodes [18],[19] is shown in Fig. 7. With the same assumptions as in Section IIIA, the g and F are given by

$$g = 4\pi^2 \left(\frac{I_{dc}^2}{V_\pi^2} \right) R_{in} R_{out} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega \tau}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$F = 1 + \frac{V_\pi^2}{4\pi^2 R_{in} \sin^2(\Omega\tau/2)} \left(\frac{1}{I_{dc}^2 R_{out}} + \frac{2e}{I_{dc} k_B T} \right), \quad (6)$$

where V_π is the voltage required to achieve π -radians phase shift in the phase modulator, Ω is the angular modulation frequency and τ is the differential delay in the MZI.

For these experiments a narrow-linewidth fiber laser (Orbits Lightwave ETH-10-1546.52) was used as the source and a 2-W PM EDFA (Keyopsys KPS-STD-BT-C-33-PM-BO-111-FA-FA) was placed either before or after the phase modulator having $V_\pi = 1.72$ V at 12 GHz (EOSPACE PM-ULTRA-PFU-PFU-NRL). A quadrature-biased MZI with $\tau = 375$ ps was placed before a pair of custom balanced photodiodes (Discovery Semiconductor DSC10M-39-FC/UPC-K-1) with a 50- Ω load-matching circuit. The G and NF were measured as in Section IIIA using an Agilent network analyzer (E5071C) and spectrum analyzer (E4448A). The results are shown in Fig. 8 and put into context in Figs. 1 and 2; to our knowledge, these experiments represent the highest- G and lowest-NF phase-modulated optical link reported. With the EDFA before the modulator, $I_{dc} = 18$ mA (9 mA per diode) with $G = -1$ dB and NF = 17.5 dB at 12 GHz. The link exhibited 10-dB of excess loss at 12 GHz, 6-dB due to the matching circuit in the diodes and 4 dB due to diode roll off. Correcting (5) and the second term in (6) for this yields a calculated $G = 0.3$ dB and NF = 9.3 dB at 12 GHz, resulting in an 8.2-dB NF penalty due to optical noise. With the EDFA after the modulator, $I_{dc} = 110$ mA and the measured $G = 16$ dB and NF = 21 dB at 12 GHz. The corresponding calculated values are $G = 16.1$ dB and NF = 2.1 dB, giving an 18.9-dB penalty in the NF.

IV. SUMMARY

We have demonstrated three architectures for low-NF and high- G analog optical links without electronic amplification and have provided simple equations for determining the upper bounds on performance. Performance among the best reported has been achieved and the lowest-NF, highest- G phase-modulated optical links have been presented. In all of the experiments, the amount of shot-noise-limited optical power available limited the NF, stressing that better optical sources and/or different techniques with present sources are required to improve on the results presented and surveyed here.

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